

ACCURATE COMPRESSION STRENGTH PREDICTIONS OF COMPOSITES FOR WIND TURBINE BLADES

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Composites Manufacturing and Testing

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- Ole V. Ferguson, DTU Wind Energy / LM Wind Power
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Pultruded profiles inside the +80 m wind turbine blades

Pultruded carbon fiber profiles

Pictures from Fiberline.com

Casted into blade moulds like this Vestas blade mould

Stress state in compression

Workflow to be presented

Fiber and matrix properties

Orientation distribution

Non-linear composite FEM

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = C_{ijkl} (V_f C_{ijkl}^{m1} C_{ijkl}^{m2} C_{ijkl}^f) \dot{\epsilon}_{kl}$$

Accurate compression prediction

Predict compression strength based on

- **Uniaxial stress-strain curve** of the fiber and matrix material
 - Ramberg-Osgood fitting
- **Material orientation** distribution determined from 3D x-ray scan
 - Python script for Structure tensor analysis
 - User-subroutine mapping using orient.f in Abaqus
- **Geometrical and material non-linear (incremental) finite element model**
 - Umat.f user-subroutine in Abaqus
- **Predict the load-deflection curve** of specific scanned samples
 - No failure criteria but based on load maximum due to material point rotations

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Mechanical properties of specific epoxy material

Ramberg-Osgood fitting

$$\epsilon_e = \frac{\sigma_e}{E} + \frac{3}{7} \frac{\sigma^{RO}}{E} \left(\frac{\sigma_e}{\sigma^{RO}} \right)^{n^{RO}}$$

Mechanical properties of the polymer matrix material

- Tension vs shear

Carbon fiber properties in **tension**

- Non-linear behaviour

Good agreement between non-linear fibers and Rule of Mixture defined composite behaviour in tension

Carbon fiber properties in compression

- back calculation from compression test of the composite

Properties of pultruded carbon fiber composite

Material properties	E [GPa]	σ_0 [MPa]	n	ν
Carbon fibers	215 ± 2	4076 ± 83	3.9 ± 0.1	0.26
Epoxy matrix	2.77 ± 0.01	68.4 ± 0.2	5.6 ± 0.1	0.4

$$V_f = 0.62$$

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3D x-ray tomography (Zeiss Versa 520) - carbon fiber composites

Scan samples

$5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ cross-section

$2 \times 2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ Field of View (FoV)

Voxel size: 1.98 microns, $d_f = 7$ microns

$1.56 \times 1.01 \times 1.77 \text{ mm}^3$ FoV

Material orientation segmentation - Structure tensor method

3D X-ray scan

Structure tensor method in 2D

- σ : Noise scale
 - computing derivatives
- ρ : Integration scale
 - averaging over the neighborhood
- Value of ρ : scale with fiber-diameter
 - Small give local orientation
 - Large captures the overall orientation
- Dominating direction is given by the smallest eigenvector

Fiber orientation in 3D

Fiber orientations in 3D

(a) 2D fiber orientation, ϕ_{2D} .

(b) 3D fiber orientation, ϕ .

Mapping orientations on 3D mesh using Python

Structure tensor segmented X-ray scan

Finite element model with 27 integration points in each element

Include file for orient.f user subroutine

```

real*8 PHI0(27,510)
DATA (PHI0(I,1), I=1,27)/ 0.017368, -0.031673, -0.014482,
& 0.018769, 0.010712, 0.010693,
& 0.014257, 0.012763, 0.018017,
& 0.035512, 0.014058, 0.023765,
& -0.015539, 0.051035, 0.029493,
& 0.023953, 0.022386, 0.025526,
& 0.014869, 0.033055, 0.021708,
& 0.026972, 0.037397, 0.031630,
& 0.026637, 0.020749, 0.006356/
DATA (PHI0(I,2), I=1,27)/ 0.011867, 0.011318, 0.040157,
& 0.012012, 0.000498, 0.003448,
& 0.025139, 0.019827, 0.018580,

real*8 THETA0(27,510)
DATA (THETA0(I,1), I=1,27)/ -0.460082, -1.008942, -1.448212,
& -0.468504, 0.951642, 0.233209,
& 0.372499, -0.511249, 0.396310,
    
```

```

SUBROUTINE ORIENT(T,NOEL,NPT,LAYER,KSPT,COORDS,BASIS,
1 ORNAME,NNODES,CNODES,JNNUM)
C
C   INCLUDE 'ABA_PARAM.INC'
C
CHARACTER*80 ORNAME
CHARACTER*256 JOBNAME, OUTDIR, FILENAME
C
DIMENSION T(3,3),COORDS(3),BASIS(3,3),CNODES(3,NNODES)
DIMENSION JNNUM(NNODES)

INCLUDE 'A01crop_THETA.f'
INCLUDE 'A01crop_PHI.f'

T(1,1) = DCOS(PHI0(NPT,NOEL))
T(1,2) = -DSIN(PHI0(NPT,NOEL))
T(1,3) = 0.
T(2,1) = DCOS(THETA0(NPT,NOEL))*DSIN(PHI0(NPT,NOEL))
T(2,2) = DCOS(THETA0(NPT,NOEL))*DCOS(PHI0(NPT,NOEL))
T(2,3) = -DSIN(THETA0(NPT,NOEL))
T(3,1) = DSIN(THETA0(NPT,NOEL))*DSIN(PHI0(NPT,NOEL))
T(3,2) = DSIN(THETA0(NPT,NOEL))*DCOS(PHI0(NPT,NOEL))
T(3,3) = DCOS(THETA0(NPT,NOEL))

RETURN
END
    
```

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Voigt: Iso-strain and rotation of fiber and matrix

$$\dot{u}_{1,1}^f = \dot{u}_{1,1}^m \quad \dot{u}_{2,1}^f = \dot{u}_{2,1}^m$$

Reuss: Iso transverse and shear stress of fiber and matrix

$$\dot{\sigma}_{22}^f = \dot{\sigma}_{22}^m \quad \dot{\sigma}_{12}^f = \dot{\sigma}_{12}^m$$

Fibres: E_f ; ν_f ; σ_f^{RO} ; n_f^{RO}

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij}^f = C_{ijkl}^f(\sigma_e^f) \dot{\epsilon}_{kl}^f$$

Matrix: E_m ; ν_m ; σ_m^{RO} ; n_m^{RO}

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij}^{m1} = C_{ijkl}^m(\sigma_e^{m1}) \dot{\epsilon}_{kl}^{m1}$$

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij}^{m2} = C_{ijkl}^m(\sigma_e^{m2}) \dot{\epsilon}_{kl}^{m2}$$

Composite: $V_f = 0.62$

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = C_{ijkl}(V_f C_{ijkl}^{m1}, C_{ijkl}^{m2}, C_{ijkl}^f) \dot{\epsilon}_{kl}$$

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Predictions in 3D

(a) 2D FE model with integration points presented in Fig. 7a.

(b) 2D→3D FE model with integration points presented in Fig. 7b.

(c) 3D FE model with integration points presented in Fig. 7c.

Modelling 3 different 2 mm FoV scans

$$\bar{\phi} \in [0.5; 1.0]^\circ$$

(a) Original fiber orientation distribution.

(b) Aligned fiber orientation distribution.

Conclusion

- Properties in model
 - Stress strain curve of matrix material
 - Stiffness of stress-strain curve for fiber material
 - Fiber volume fraction
 - Fiber orientation distribution
- Finite Element Model
 - Non-linear composite material model
 - No failure criteria, load maximum due to local material point rotation during loading

Prediction

- Realistic compression strength predictions
- Show high dependency on small rotation with respect to the overall fiber orientation

Larger FoV using lab based X-ray scattering techniques

Composites for wind energy: Manufacturing, operation and end-of-life

4 - 7 September 2023

The focus of the 43rd Risø Symposium is on composites for wind energy. This symposium takes a life cycle perspective and addresses manufacturing, performance during operation and end-of-life of composites for wind energy. Over the last 40 years, wind turbine blades have grown an order of magnitude. Today, the longest blades are exceeding 100 meters and weighing 50 tons. Because of this growth in blade size, the cost of wind energy can now compete with fossil-based energy sources on market terms.

As society is thriving towards a zero-emission future, the wind energy sector is foreseen to further expand. Longer wind turbine blades with improved overall lifetime, reliability, recyclability, sustainability, operability and maintainability are some of the objectives set on this component. To address these upcoming and ambitious requirements, the symposium welcomes contribution dedicated to the manufacturing, the operation and performance, as well as end-of-life strategies for wind turbine blades.

Important Dates

15 March 2023: Abstract submission

01 July 2023: Paper submission

<https://www.morressier.com/call-for-papers/63ff34e08d36d800127feb22>

31 August 2023: Registration deadline

Manufacturing

Characterization and development of manufacturing processes for wind turbine blades

Existing and alternative manufacturing technologies, constrains and new opportunities, process characterization, cure kinetics and residual stresses, modelling, manufacturing defects, repair.

Operation

Experimental characterization, mechanical properties and performance of composites for wind turbine blades

Structural design and performance of blade structures; Key composite design properties: stiffness, strength, fracture and fatigue resistance; Materials development: hybrid, bio-based, thermoplastic composites and smart materials; adhesive joints and fibre/matrix interfaces; Leading edge erosion, repair, structural health monitoring. Micro and macro structural characterization using X-ray tomography and ultrasound; Novel test methods for composites under static and cyclic loading; development of test methods for structural elements, e.g. ply-drops and wrinkles, and full-scale testing of blades.

End-of-life

Strategies to address the end-of-life challenges of composites and of wind turbine blades

Reuse and lifetime extension, recyclable composite, composite recycling processes, repurposing, decommissioning, life-cycle analysis (LCA). Recycling of manufacturing waste and end-of-use wind turbines, recycling processes and products incorporating recycled materials, material substitution in wind turbine blades increasing the recycled content.

Registration

The registration fee is DKK 4500 (approx. EUR 600), and covers access to lectures, lunch and refreshments all days, conference dinner, and social arrangements. The registration fee for students is DKK 2000 (approx. EUR 270).

Contact

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 Justine Beauson, Chairwoman
 E-mail: symp43@windenergy.dtu.dk
 Website: <https://wind.dtu.dk/about/symposium-on-materials-science>

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Key dates

Registration deadline: 15 July 2023
(limited number of participants, first come – first served)
Poster abstracts by: 15 August 2023

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